

“A Study of Analysis of Growth on Implementation of Goods and Service Tax (GST) During Last 5 Years (Up to March 2022)

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Abstract

The paper tries to analyse the impact of the Automation on the various processes and procedures of GST during the last 5 years till June 30th, 2022. The paper has studied the data related to various parameters which would help us to conclude about the performance of GST during the said span. The various parameters included in the study are Registrations done, Returns filed , E Way bills generated Revenue generated. Various parameters may have shown an increasing trend and few may have shown a decrease. The changes(increase) in the rates of taxes and additional inclusions under the taxability of GST as well as COVID 19 have impacted a lot on the GST performance . Furthering more, the pace has enhanced due to increased automation in GST .

Keywords: GST, Revenue, returns, Registration, E Way Bills ,Refund.

Introduction

Goods and service tax known as GST was introduced from 1st July,2017. The Goods and Service Tax Act was passed in the Parliament on 29th March 2017. GST was first proposed by Mr Atal Bihari Vajpayee where the Task force had

recommended the implementation of GST. Later in 2006, the Finance Minister proposed to introduce the GST from 1st of April 2010. The sequence of incidences till adoption of GST has been given below :

2007	Rates of CST were reduced from 3% to 2%.
2008	Dual structure of GST with separate Levy and Legislation
2011	Computerization of commercial Taxes
2012-2015	Re introduction of GST Bill
2016	GSTN was made live
2017	4 bills passed in Lok Sabha & approved by the Cabinet
	GST implemented on 1 st July, 2017

GST has subsumed many taxes such as –

1. Excise duty
2. VAT/CST
3. Service tax
4. Additional duty of Customs and Special Additional duty in Customs.

The main idea behind the implementation of GST was “One nation One Tax”. Currently GST is the only indirect tax in India on a domestic level. GST is a comprehensive tax, levied on goods and services at each stage of value addition. GST is a tax levied at every point of sale. In the case of intra-state sales, Central GST and State GST are charged. All the inter-state sales are chargeable to the Integrated GST. In case of the Union Territories, the State GST is replaced by UTGST. GST is a destination based tax because the tax is levied at the point of sale and at place of consumption.

For example, a sale takes place from Gujarat to Rajasthan, then the final consumer being in Rajasthan, the tax will be levied by Rajasthan.

Benefits of GST are enumerated below:-

1. The principle of “One nation one tax”.
2. To eliminate or remove the cascading effect of taxes.

3. To reduce the evasion of taxes.
4. To enhance the tax payer base.
5. To ease the process of doing business.
6. To enhance the consumption and endorse competitive pricing.
7. To regulate the unorganized sector.
8. To enhance the efficiency in logistics.

GST and Technology

The adoption of GST was itself an example of the human efforts being replaced by Technology. The GSTN i.e the GST network is an authentication of the same. The Automation is nothing but the replacement of human efforts being replaced by the Technological applications. With the adoption of GST, various processes and procedures of manual intervention have been replaced by the automated processes through various software's .There is a lot of information flowing freely from various sources and perspectives. Different data requires different treatment at different levels so as to fulfill the requirements and compliances The data compiled and processed by these softwares can be easily uploaded on the GST portal by logging in . The data processed by these softwares is compatible for direct uploading thereby saving the time and proving cost

effective. These changes were also necessary due to the sudden emergence of COVID 19 which had made it difficult to complete the processes in a physical mode .

In this paper we study the performance of GST in the last five years on the basis of the following parameters :

1. Registrations
2. E Way Bill Generation
3. Filing of returns
4. Revenue Collection
5. Contribution from various forms of business in the overall revenue generation.
6. Refunds issued

Rationale of the Research

We know that today we are in an era of highly impactful technologies. Each day begins with advent of some new technology. GST generates a lot of revenue for the fiduciary on account of taxes in India. We study the correlation between the changes that have occurred in the past 5 years (Increase/ Decrease) on account of various parameters stated below and its impact on performance of GST. The various parameters chosen for the study are –

1. Registrations
2. E Way Bill Generation
3. Filing of returns
4. Revenue Collection
5. Contribution from various forms of business in the overall revenue generation .
6. Refunds issued

Objective of the research:

1. To critically analyze the financial impact of GST .

2. To study the impact of non-financial impact of GST.

Research Methodology –

1. **Research Design** – This is an Analytical The main purpose of this research is to analyze the performance of various procedures and compliances in GST using the automation.
2. **Sampling Design:** As the research is based on secondary data and is an analysis of data available on the online sources , there is no scope for sampling design.
3. **Data Processing and Analysis:**
 1. Critical review of literature and historical events.
 2. Identifying gap in the existing field of knowledge.

Hypothesis

“There has been a good financial growth on account of GST implementation in the past 5 years”.

Data Analysis

The data for analysing the performance of GST in last 5 years has been collected from the official report of the government published on its website - <https://www.gst.gov.in/download/gststatistics>. The analysis is based on the data available on the website . The various parameters chosen have been studied individually and correlated with the growth of GST.

Registrations

The trend of Registrations from April 2020 to June 2022 has been depicted in the chart below:

Source : <https://www.gst.gov.in/download/gststatistics>

From the above chart, we find that the registrations have increased from April 20 to June 2022 thereby having higher number of active tax payers in the present times. These registrations are net of the cancellations that have occurred during

the given period. The total tax payers as on June 2022 have reached the number of 1.40 crores as in June 2022.

A further study of registrations from 30th June 2022 to 31st January 2023 are depicted below :

Year	Number of Active Tax payers
31.01.2023	1,37,89,304

30.06.2022

1,38,29,686

The above chart depicts that there has been an increase in the number of taxpayers from June 30, 2022 to 31st January 2023. This is an indication that more businesses have been registered and hence it will also have a corresponding impact on the revenue as well.

E Way Bills

We know that E Way bill is necessary for the GST registered persons having a taxable value

of goods over 50,000. E way bill indicates that there has been a movement of goods indicating huge amount of transactions that may have taken place.

The E Way Bill needs to be generated in the following cases :

1. Supply of goods
2. Return of Goods
3. Transfer between branches

E-way bill Statistics

Functionalities	1 st April 2021 To 31 st March 2022	1 st April 2022 To 30 th June 2022
Total e-Way Bills generated	77,38,77,511	22,33,40,497
Count of Inter State e-Way Bills	30,34,94,161	8,41,43,173
Count of Intra State e-Way bills	47,03,83,350	13,91,97,324

Total Number of E-way Bill generated	280,05,92,362	From Apr 2018 to Jun 2022
Highest number of e-Way bill generated in a day	32,87,109	On 31 st March 2022
Number of Tax payers registered with e-Way bill system *	41,80,323	As on 30 th June 2022
Number of Transporters registered with e-Way bill system	67,959	

* Out of 1,38,27,412 registered taxpayers

Source : <https://www.gst.gov.in/download/gststatistics>

From the above chart we find that almost 77 crores of E Way bills have been generated during the FY 2021-22 and 22 crores of E Way bills have been generated during the last six months till June 2022 in the current Financial year 2022-23. If we see the number of E Way bills generated from April 2018 to June 2022, the number is around 280 crores.

Roughly if we calculate the number of E Way Bills generated during the span April 18 to April 21 calculates to 280 crores -77 crores = 203 crores.

Therefore we see that there is high generation of E Way bills during the last 5 years indicating a good performance of GST.

Return Filing- GSTR 1

The GSTR 1 return of GST is to be filed mandatorily by all the registered persons. It relates to the outward supplies of the taxpayers during a month/ quarter as per the scheme of return filing adopted by the supplier.

Source : <https://www.gst.gov.in/download/gststatistics>

The chart above indicates the number of returns filed by the taxpayers during the period starting July 2019 and ending May 2022. We observe that in the first years, the gap between the eligible tax filers and actual tax payers was more as compared to the later years. Secondly, the tax filers are more at the end of each quarter as compared to the other months as in the quarter ends, the tax payers filing under monthly and quarterly scheme are filing returns.

To talk in numbers we can say that almost in July 2019, 30 lakh tax payers filed returns whereas the number reached 70 lakh of tax payers in April 22. This is with reference to the monthly tax payers.

Similarly when we speak of monthly and quarterly tax payers taken together, in Sep 2019, the

number was near to 1.1 crores which increased to 1.2 crores in March 2022.

This rise again is in line with the increase in registrations and E Way bill generation which indicates that more tax payers have been covered under the net of GST.

Return Filing- GSTR 3B

The GSTR3B return of GST is basically a declaration of summary of return filed every month by the tax payers. IT is to be filed even in case of Nil taxes. It is not allowed to revise the return once filed. The following people are exempted from filing the above return :

1. Input service distributors
2. Non residents who are taxable
3. Taxpayers registered under the Composition scheme

Source : <https://www.gst.gov.in/download/gststatistics>

The above chart shows the compliance of the tax payers on account of GSTR 3 B on a monthly and quarterly basis. We see that the number of tax payers filing returns late are more than the number of tax payers filing returns on timely basis. We can see that the percentage of tax payers filing timely returns is about 65-70% whereas the defaulters are in the bracket of 35-40%. Hence a collection of late fee must also have

been done on account of delayed filing. However the financial impact of the same has not been considered in this study.

Revenue Collection

The tax paid by the tax payers under GST has been depicted in the graph below. The tax payment indicates the money paid by the tax payers under the GST regime. It includes the data from Quarter 2 of 2017-18 till the quarter 4 of the

financial year 2021-22. The GST was implemented from 1st July 2017 and hence there is no data for the same for the quarter 1 of 2017-18.

In quarter 2 we also have the tax payers who have shifted from the earlier regime to the GST regime and hence there is an impact on the collection for the same.

We see that in Quarter 2, the collection of taxes was around 211 thousand crores whereas it increased to 661 thousand crores in the quarter 4 of the FY 2021-22. Hence we see that there is almost a 313% growth in the revenue over the span of last 4 years which is highly commendable.

The growth is not only because of the growth in the business but also because of the increase in the rates of few commodities. However major component of growth has occurred due to increase in the number of tax payers who are required to pay taxes under GST under domestic supplies as well as imports.

The total composition also indicates that IGST(Integrated GST) collected during the Inter state sales is the highest as compared to SGST(State GST), CGST (Central GST), Cess in all the quarters of the past 4 years.

Source : <https://www.gst.gov.in/download/gststatistics>

Contribution from various forms of business in the overall revenue generation

Under this parameter, we study the various tax payers who have contributed towards the revenue under GST. The various forms of business organisations contributing towards the GST revenue according to the chart below are:

1. Public limited companies
2. Private limited companies
3. Proprietorship
4. Partnership Firms
5. Limited liability partnership
6. Public Sector Undertakings
7. Government Departments
8. Others

We can see that the highest contribution is from the public limited companies (35%)

whereas they are only 1% of the total tax payer population. Second in the line of contribution are Private limited companies being 6% of the tax payer population and contributing about 28% to the revenue.

The highest of the tax payer population are the proprietorship firms (80%) and they contribute only 13% to the total revenue. Next in line are the partnership firms who constitute to 11% of the tax payers and contribute 7% to the revenue.

The Public Sector Undertakings contribute to 10% to the total revenue. This indicates that the proprietary firms registered under GST are voluntary registered but not having much liability as the turnover is less.

Source : <https://www.gst.gov.in/download/gststatistics>

Refunds

The refund can be claimed by a tax payer only if the GSTR 3B and GSTR1 returns are filed. The various refunds that can be claimed under GST broadly consist of the following components :

1. Excessive tax deposited
2. Excess ITC which is accumulated and remains non utilized due to no liability of tax
3. Refund of IGST in exports

The chart below shows that the refunds issued by the Government on account of GST since 2019. Refunds of about Rs. 2 crores have been disbursed by the Government in the past 5 years against 7 lakh number of applications of refunds during the span. Thus in comparison to the revenue collection of year ended March 2022 (Rs. 2,358 thousand crores) we can say that refunds are (Rs 225 thousand crores). The refunds constitute around 9 % of the collection .

Online Refund Status: As on 30th June, 2022

#	STATUS	COUNT	AMOUNT (IN CR.)	EXPLANATION
1	Total application received since 26/06/2019 (H-RFD-01)	11,31,524	3,98,051	
2	Total applications withdrawn	18,413	5,881.67	
3	Filed, but yet to be acknowledged (RFD-02)	21,278	6,990	
4	Out of (1-3-2) above, cases where deficiency memo issued (RFD-03)	2,56,892	79,405.77	
4	Cases which are at various stages of processing (1-2-3-4)	6,35,242	2,74,769.95	Percentage of 6,35,242 ↓ Percentage of 2,74,769.95 ↓
5	Out of 4 above, cases which have been acknowledged but no further processing has started	19,085	1,087.49	2.26% 1.85%
6	Out of 4 above, cases where Provisional Order has been issued (RFD-04)	1,371	1,184.88	0.18% 0.41%
7	Out of 4 above, (RFD-06) issued	8,04,589	258386.24	96.22% 94.02%
8	Out of 4 above, cases where SCN has been issued which have not been replied (RED-08)	4,930	1,367.81	0.59% 0.50%
9	Out of 8 above, cases where SCN has been replied and case under process (RFD-09)	5,819	2,735.11	0.80% 1.00%
10	Number of Payment Order issued in RFD-05	7,87,804	2,31,349.98	Percentage of 787,804 ↓ Percentage of 231,349.98 ↓
11	Out of (10) above, Disbursed by PFMS	7,67,072	2,25,832.60	97.17% 97.62%

Conclusions

The goods and services tax system are highly comprehensive , integrated and user friendly . The process has become even easier as the compliance part can be met with the automation for up to 80% of the processes.

The GST has had a good financial performance can be concluded from the data analysed above .

1. The tax payer base has increased over the past 5 years which indicates that businesses and transactions under GST have grown helping the Indian economy to grow.
2. The E way bill generation has also been quite good and shows an increasing trend indicating again increase in the transactions under GST .
3. The returns filed for GSTR 3 B and GSTR 1 also indicate that the compliances are duly met

by 65% to 70% of the tax payers and delays occur on part of the rest of the tax payers. A corresponding increase in return filed is observed on account of increased tax payer base

4. The revenue collections have shown a 313% increase over the past 5 years (Quarter 2 of F Y 2017-18 to Quarter 4 of March 2022).
5. We see that the maximum contribution in tax payment is done by the Public and private limited companies. Both together contribute to 63% of the revenue. Balance 37% is generated by other forms of the business . Here we also find that proprietorship firms have taken voluntary registrations as they consist of 80% of the population of tax payers but their contribution is only 6%. We can say that there could be major growth in revenue from these tax payers in near future as they may have registered only as they know they would be required to pay taxes in the near future based on their revenue projections.
6. The refunds have also been made by the Government in the past 5 years . If we see that

proportion of the total refunds made in 2022 as a % of turnover it comes to 9% of the revenue collected for the year ended March 2022.

Suggestions/recommendations

It is recommended that the Government should also publish the data relating to the penalties charged by it during the past 5 years . Also it should give the data for registrations in a year wise manner on the website for ease of study and to analyse the Y-O-Y growth for better analysis

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